

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER TO THE FISHING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Technology transfer is considered to be a partnership function of government and industry composed of the following steps:

1. Identify fishery needs;
2. Identify technology to satisfy the needs;
3. Conduct adequate technology testing to define the potential benefits;
4. Package the technology for transfer;
5. Initiate technology transfer by assisting early adopters.

vessels shrimping off the south Atlantic states use single trawls on each side.

Another example of an improved fishing device that has not yet been adopted by the fishery is the Trawling Efficiency Device (TED) developed by the National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS). This device (see Figure 1) was developed to provide protection for sea turtles. These animals, protected under the Endangered Species Act (ESA), are captured in shrimp trawls and many drown. The TED eliminates the capture of at least 97% of the sea turtles, while achieving a shrimp catch equal to or better than a standard unmodified net.

During development it became apparent that the device had additional benefits, such as reducing bycatch (non-target species and trash). A small portion of the catch may be retained and sold, but most of the bycatch is discarded, since it is generally viewed as a nuisance and represents additional labor to separate it from the shrimp.

The TED uses a trap door in the top of the device to release sea turtles. However, test data show that TED also excludes unwanted items such as jelly balls, horseshoe crabs, sharks, skates, sponges, etc. This part of the catch is particularly unwanted, and if caught in large quantities reduces tow times and may damage the shrimp catch. Further studies indicate that the device reduces the overall drag of a trawl, which should translate into a fuel savings.

One more important benefit of TED is its ability to actually increase shrimp catch in a trawl an average of 7.5%. Notwithstanding the other benefits, this positive result could have immediate benefits to the shrimping industry. At an initial cost of about \$400 for each trawl, shrimp vessels could very quickly recover the initial cost of TEDs and in the long range improve the profitability of their fishing operation. Thus, out of a problem that may have seriously impacted the shrimp industry, a development occurred that could have several long-term benefits to the industry while at the same time protecting the sea turtles.

1. Introduction

Significant advances have been made during the past 30 years in all areas of marine technology. This is particularly true in electronics. Fishing vessels of even moderate size now have depth recorders, fish scopes, LORAN and satellite navigational equipment, radar, radios, and other specialized electronic gear. The advantages of these devices to fishermen are obvious. They can increase profits and enhance safety. A percentage of fishermen have the latest gear and use it to their advantage. These are called highliners by other fishermen.

Utilization of new fishing gear does not appear to diffuse through the industry as rapidly as the new sophisticated fish finding and navigation equipment. This is particularly true of the southeast United States shrimp industry that is composed of many relatively small companies and single entrepreneurs. Twin shrimp trawls on both sides of a vessel are the most fuel efficient means of catching shrimp--yet these trawls are used almost exclusively in the Gulf of Mexico. Most

2. Technology Transfer

Since the use of the TED appears to offer a more cost effective way to produce shrimp, rapid utilization by shrimpers should be expected. Such has not been the case. Some of the excuses offered by shrimpers include: it is not an off-the-shelf item; the initial cost is too high; it will be hard to handle in rough weather; it takes up too much room; and it won't work for different sizes and types of trawls. How can technology be propagated past these objections?

Rogers and Shoemaker (1971) have summarized the communication of innovations. Adoption of innovations follows a normal distribution composed of innovators, early adopters, early and late majority, laggards and non-adopters. Innovators are basically gadgeteers who may not have profitable businesses. Early adopters generally are the highliners who do well financially. The early and late majority are the average operators who follow the early adopters. The laggards adopt new ideas only after a considerable observation period and non-adopters do not accept new methods. The problem in transferring new technology is to get to the early adopters--most of the others will follow. Innovation diffusion in the fishing industry has not been studied extensively; but we know from research in agriculture and other areas that early and late adopters can be differentiated according to such factors as size of operation, education, social status, age, information sources, etc.

In the Southeast Region, NMFS is now attempting to reach the early adopters by giving shipboard TED demonstrations, distributing brochures and Sea Grant marine agent presentations using TED models, and using other visual aids. In addition to this general approach, a combination of NMFS and Gulf and South Atlantic Fisheries Development Foundation funding is being used to construct TEDs for use by early adopters. These TEDs are being constructed and distributed by Desco Marine of St. Augustine, Florida.

3. Future Technology Transfer Programs

The TED technology transfer program in the southeast is now serving as a model to evaluate requirements for future technology transfer projects. If it is successful and the results are positive, many other opportunities for fishery assistance exist. A good example is an electric shrimp trawl system developed during the late 1960s. This system allows daytime as well as nighttime shrimping in some areas. Furthermore, research results indicate that nighttime catches can be increased 30-40%. Original objections to the system were cost and operational problems associated with getting power from the deck to under water units via conductor cables. An overall economic analysis based on additional controlled testing should now show a favorable cost/benefit ratio. Power supply problems can also be overcome through present technology.

Other areas that could be enhanced include shipboard navigation, communication, and fish finding equipment. Microcomputers could be used to calibrate and integrate equipment to conserve fuel and time.

4. Reference

Rogers, E.M. and F.F. Shoemaker (1971). Communication of Innovations: A Cross Cultural Approach. New York, N.Y. The Free Press.

Figure 1.